

EFFECTIVENESS OF THEME WRITING IN IMPROVING THE LEVEL OF ENGLISH WRITING PROFICIENCY AMONG GRADE 11 LEARNERS AT BANTAD NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative study aimed to improve the English writing proficiency level of Grade 11 learners in various constructs: Content, Structure, Lexico-grammatical, and Mechanics using the Theme Writing through the quasi-experimental method. Data were gathered from the first and last written output of the 26 enrolled TVL- Agri-fishery Arts learners at Bantad National High School and analyzed through Paired T-test using SPSS. The analysis revealed that their writing proficiency across all constructs was at the "Beginning" level with mean scores ranging from 1.19 to 1.31 in the first written output. While, in the last written output using the Theme Writing notebook, the result showed improvement in all construct as the means score ranged from 2.27-2.85 which fell under the "Developing" to "Approaching Proficiency" level. Moreover, comparing the first and last written compositions revealed significant improvements in content, structure, lexico-grammatical, and mechanics with p-values of 0.001 indicating that the differences were statistically significant. Therefore, the findings suggest the revival of Theme Writing and its inclusion in the curriculum to improve the writing proficiency level of the SHS students.

Key words: *Theme Writing, English writing proficiency level, content, structure, lexico-grammatical, mechanics*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, being a proficient writer is necessary for many positions in a future profession. This holds even in cases where written language creates the initial impression. A well-written, well-structured, and grammatically accurate email, letter, text message, or social media post will leave a positive impression on the reader about the author. As one of the productive skills, writing is one of the fundamental skills for it reflects the level of language competence, which starts with introducing the English language to alphabets and numbers and advances to sentence formation, grammar, vocabulary, etc. (Pearson India, 2022). Thus, writing abilities are something that every learner should learn.

The Department of Education (DepEd), as prescribed by Republic Act 10533, introduced three new English subjects: Reading and Writing Skills, English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP), and Oral Communication in Context with target performance standards and learning competencies. Based on the curriculum guide of these subjects, the Senior High School (SHS) learners are expected to write a comprehensive review /reaction paper; produce a well-balanced concept paper in a specific discipline; produce each type of academic writing and professional correspondence following the properties of well-written texts and process approach to writing; and writes a 250-word essay of his/her objective observation and evaluation of the various speakers watched and listened to.

However, some Senior High School (SHS) students have difficulties with their writing skills. In particular, a study conducted among Senior High Schools in Alamada, Cotabato, by Callora and Suñas (2023) revealed that student writing proficiency was still developing. Their proficiency in the areas of Content and Structure was classified as Approaching Proficiency, while Lexico-grammatical Ability and Mechanics were rated as Developing. The study further indicated that among the students, 1% were Novice, 28% were Intermediate, 48% were Refined, 19% were Superior, and only 4% were Distinguished writers. According to Shaw (2023), featured in the Philippine Daily Inquirer, only 6% of Filipinos met the expected writing proficiency for their grade level, while nearly half were placed in the lowest proficiency level. Specifically, Grade 11 students at Bantad National High School in Gumaca, Quezon, during the 2023-2024 school year, were involved in various writing prompts. Their first written outputs showed writing proficiency with an average score of 62% for Content; 55% for Structure; 70% for Grammar, and 68% for Mechanics, all of which fell under the Beginning level. Moreover, only 32% of the 32 enrolled students in Grade 11 under the Technology Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track, specifically in the Agri-fishery strand, passed their first written output for evaluation. This problem is also evident at the University of Saint Anthony in Iriga City, where students exhibited more errors in subject-verb agreement, proper usage of tenses, organization of thoughts, contracted words, and the distribution of ideas per sentence. Additionally, according to Hikma et al. (2019) errors in mechanics were noted, including incorrect punctuation, capitalization of proper nouns, paragraph indentation, and sentence breaks among students.

In response to these challenges, the researcher aims to improve the writing proficiency of SHS students using Theme Writing. In 1978, Eugenio et al. stated that a Theme Writing is a written exercise designed to produce quality written output. A theme represents the written expression of one's thoughts, ideas, opinions, impressions, reflections, beliefs, feelings, emotions, and moods about oneself and the world in general.

In the late 19th century, teachers commonly used Theme Writing compositions to assess students' writing skills. Examples of such themes include "My Most Unforgettable Moment"; "My Summer Vacation"; "Who Am I?" and "The Christmas Celebration." According to G. Ricafrente (personal communication, March 17, 2024), teachers need to review the student's outputs and provide appropriate corrections regarding structure, format, and organization to avoid repeating the same mistakes in future assignments. This feedback can be most effective in the classroom after a lesson, ensuring the academic integrity of student's written work. Also, Ricafrente highlighted journal writing as a valuable writing exercise, where teachers assign topics for students to ponder and write about in their journals. In addition, R. Bacobe (personal communication, June 8, 2024) emphasized the importance of Theme Writing in improving the writing skills of students, noting that it helped her learn proper capitalization, spelling, indentation, margin use, and correct grammar, as well as to write legibly and neatly. She mentioned that teachers provided topics for students to write reflections or essays about, either weekly or daily. Also, most participants in the online interview conducted by the researcher regarding their experiences with Theme Writing agreed that it was highly effective. They commented on the impacts of Theme Writing on their lives, such as increased awareness of proper margins and indentation, learning to write in cursive, and developing strong discipline in writing, as well as being able to express their feelings through specific themes (Netizens, personal communication, June 7, 2024). Additionally, L. Gwen (personal communication, June 9, 2024) emphasized the growing use of ChatGPT among students for their written outputs.

Moreover, in Piaget's Constructivist Theory (1973), as cited by Mcleod (2023), which asserts that "knowledge is gained through the process of action, reflection, and construction," emphasizes the interaction between experiences and ideas in creating new knowledge. In this context, Theme Writing can be viewed as a constructivist approach, as students must rewrite their work after receiving feedback on their Theme entries and resubmit for further review. This process allows learners to recognize and correct their mistakes, facilitating the integration of prior knowledge with newly acquired insights from the teacher's feedback. This reflects the learners' active role in their knowledge acquisition.

Therefore, the researcher employed Theme Writing to help SHS students improve their writing proficiency in content, lexico-grammatical ability, structure, and mechanics.

Research Questions

The study determined the effectiveness of Theme Writing in improving the level of English writing proficiency among Grade 11 learners at Bantad National High School as basis for the proposed curriculum content.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of writing proficiency of the Grade 11 learners during the first written composition per construct in terms of:
 - 1.1 content;
 - 1.2 structure;
 - 1.3 lexico-grammatical; and
 - 1.4 mechanics?
2. What is the level of writing proficiency of the Grade 11 learners during the last written composition per construct in terms of:
 - 2.1 content;
 - 2.2 structure;
 - 2.3 lexico-grammatical; and
 - 2.4 mechanics?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of writing proficiency in the first and last written composition of the respondents?
4. What program for the revival of Theme Writing in the curriculum could be proposed by the researcher based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study is quantitative as it involved collecting and analyzing numerical data. Quantitative research design is a systematic investigation of phenomena by gathering quantifiable data and using statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques (Fleetwood, 2023). Specifically, this study used a quasi-experimental method to establish a cause-and-effect link between the independent and dependent variables. No randomization or control groups were necessary. Theme writing was employed as the treatment for Grade 11 students, and the differences between their first and final written outputs were examined.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Bantad National High School (BNHS), located in the 4th Congressional District, Brgy. Bantad, Municipality of Gumaca, Province of Quezon. BNHS is the farthest secondary school in the Gumaca East District, situated 26 kilometers away from the town proper of Gumaca, Quezon. The school comprises both Junior High School and Senior High School levels. Currently, it has two non-teaching staff members and eleven teaching personnel: Eight (8) teachers in the Junior High School department

and Three (3) in the Senior High School department. BNHS is considered one of the more remote areas in Gumaca, Quezon, contributing to unstable internet access.

The researcher conducted the study in this school due to the following reasons: first, the need for improvement in writing skills among the learners in BNHS is highly evident and seen as one of the problems in the SHS department. Next, the researcher is the only English teacher in the SHS department and witnessed the problem in the writing skills of the respondents. Lastly, the number of target respondents in this school is enough for the experts to easily monitor and check the performance in writing through theme writing as scheduled.

Population and Sampling

The respondents of this study were the 26 enrolled Grade 11 learners from Bantad National High School under the TVL track—Agri-Fishery Arts strand—and selected through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling (also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling) is a technique in which the researcher relies on their own judgment to choose members of the population to participate in the study (Saunders et al., 2012). The respondents were personally selected by the researcher for several reasons such as: they are the researcher's students, they need improvement in their writing skills, they lack motivation for writing academic papers, and they have fundamental gaps in their knowledge of how to write simple essays.

Research Instrument

In order to obtain the data for this study, the researcher administered to the respondents a writing activity that was checked by the expert in the field of language teaching using the adapted analytic rubric for scoring developed by Callora and Suñas (2023). Thus, it underwent content validation by experts due to modifications made by the researcher. Also, the researcher was permitted to use and modify the borrowed instrument for the appropriateness of theme writing. The written tasks were based on the monthly celebration here in the Philippines, such as “My Vacation” for July, “My Hero” for August, “Peace be with you” in September, and “My Best Teacher” for October. The essay as a response should have consisted of at least three paragraphs. These responses served as written outputs and were evaluated by an expert through an analytical rubric.

Specifically, the criteria for assessing students' outputs in this study is as follows (Callora & Suñas, 2023): *Content*. In essay writing, content and structure are essential to fully establish the purpose of writing –content deals with reflecting and developing the topic of the essay. The topic and its details should be discussed in the content to make a meaningful essay. The content should also consider the needs, interests, and expectations of the readers. *Structure*. The essay's structure deals with the organization of thoughts. The organization should be logical for the essay to be easily understood. Each part of the essay should function effectively as in the introduction, body, and conclusion to maintain the quality of the essay. *Lexico-grammatical Ability*. It deals with error free in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of preposition, and articles in essay writing. Lastly, the *Mechanics*. It means the correct spelling, capitalization,

punctuation, and formatting. These elements are found essential because they could also affect the meaning and the entire quality of an output.

Furthermore, the level of proficiency set by DepEd Order no. 73 s. 2012 is the basis of the adopted analytic rubric for scoring. Students in the *Beginning* (B) level have difficulty understanding because they have not developed or acquired the necessary prerequisite and foundational knowledge and/or abilities. Although they have the bare minimum of fundamental information, abilities, and comprehension; students at the *Developing* (D) level require assistance to do real-world tasks. As they acquire the essential knowledge, abilities, and core understanding; students at the *Approaching Proficiency* (AP) level can apply these understandings through real-world performance challenges with minimal help from their teachers and/or peers. Students at the *Proficient* level gain the fundamental knowledge, skills, and basic comprehension that they can use independently through practical performance assignments; and students at the *Advanced* (A) level have the knowledge, skills, and essential understandings that go beyond the requirements.

Table 1. Analytic Rubric for Theme Writing composition

CRITERIA	ADVANCED (5)	PROFICIENT (4)	APPROACHING PROFICIENCY (3)	DEVELOPING (2)	BEGINNING (1)
CONTENT	The theme or central idea is very clear and well supported with accurate information. There is one specific focused topic, and important details were discussed comprehensively. The title is greatly connected to the theme and topic itself.	The theme or central idea is clear and adequately supported with reasonably accurate information. There is one specific topic, and details were generally discussed. The title is connected to the theme and topic itself.	The theme or central idea is somewhat clear and minimally supported with somewhat accurate information. The topic is reflected, and details were seen in the essay but there is relative absence of independent thought. The title is somewhat connected to the theme and topic itself.	The theme or central idea is slightly clear and accurate information are barely noticeable. There is more than one topic reflected with somewhat vague details resulting to confusion. The title is inconsistent with the theme and topic itself.	The theme or central idea is barely noticeable. There are no apparent topic sentences. Details are either wrong or lacking. The title, theme and topic itself do not relate to the process.
STRUCTURE	There is a complete organization of thoughts with the three main parts of the essay (introduction, body, and conclusion) precisely presented. Appropriate transitional devices were used to provide a well cohered or logical presentation of ideas.	There is an organization of thoughts with the three main parts of the essay (introduction, body, and conclusion) moderately presented. Adequate transitional devices were used to provide a cohered or logical presentation of ideas.	There is an organization of thoughts with the three main parts of the essay (introduction, body, and conclusion) fairly presented. Minimal transitional devices were used to provide a cohered or logical presentation of ideas.	The organization of thoughts with the three main parts of the essay (introduction, body, and conclusion) was barely presented. Most of the transitional devices used to provide a cohered or logical presentation of ideas are inappropriate.	The whole composition is unorganized and under develop that clearly shows the need for improvement.
LEXICO-GRAMMATICAL	The theme writing composition is free from any grammatical errors such as, subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of linking, auxiliary, and modal verbs, and proper use of pronoun-antecedent agreement.	Only few errors are shown in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of linking, auxiliary, and modal verbs, and proper use of pronoun-antecedent agreement.	Some errors are shown in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of linking, auxiliary, and modal verbs, and proper use of pronoun-antecedent agreement.	Errors are clearly shown in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of linking, auxiliary, and modal verbs, and proper use of pronoun-antecedent agreement.	Errors in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of linking, auxiliary, and modal verbs, and proper use of pronoun-antecedent agreement are evidently present that lead to misunderstanding of the content.
MECHANICS	The writing is free from any error in terms of spelling, capitalization, punctuation or formatting (e.g. margin, spacing, and indentation)	The writing contains only few errors in, spelling, capitalization, punctuation or (e.g. margin, spacing, and indentation).	The writing contains some errors in spelling, capitalization, punctuation (e.g. margin, spacing, and indentation).	The writing is readable, but contains several errors in spelling, capitalization, punctuation or (e.g. margin, spacing, and indentation).	The writing is unreadable because of errors in spelling, capitalization, punctuation or (e.g. margin, spacing, and indentation).

Data Gathering Procedures

A letter requesting permission was submitted to the School Division Superintendent, Public School District Supervisor, and School Head of BNHS. On the first day of school, the researcher conducted the initial writing composition with the theme centered on the respondents' previous vacation. They were given 60 minutes to complete

the writing activity, which was then collected to evaluate their performance using an analytic rubric by an expert.

In the following week, theme writing was introduced to the respondents with a clear explanation of its purpose and how it would be evaluated by the expert. The theme writing notebook differed from the traditional formal theme book, providing more space for the content of the written activities. The original corrected writing activity was returned to the learners, who rewrote it in their theme writing notebook, incorporating revisions based on the identified mistakes from their original output. This revised piece was rechecked using the scoring rubric.

This process was repeated four (4) times for theme writing and eight times with revisions for each topic. The fourth topic, with a themed “My Best Teacher,” served as their final written output. Finally, the collected scores from the first and last written outputs were interpreted and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher employed various statistical measures to analyze the collected data. For Problems I and II, the mean was calculated to determine the proficiency level of the respondents.

To get the mean:

$$M = \frac{fx}{N}$$

where: fx = summation of frequency

N = number of respondents

Level of Competency	Scale	Range
Advanced (A)	5	4.21 - 5.00
Proficient (P)	4	3.41 - 4.20
Approaching Proficiency (AP)	3	2.61 - 3.40
Developing (D)	2	1.81 - 2.60
Beginning (B)	1	1.0 - 1.80

While for problem III, using the SPSS, Paired T-test was used in treating the collected data to measure the significant difference between the first and last written compositions.

RESULTS

Part I. The Level of English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Learners During the First Written Composition Per Construct.

Table 2

The Level of English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Learners During the First Written Composition Per Construct

Constructs	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content	1.31	Beginning
Structure	1.23	Beginning
Lexico-Grammatical	1.19	Beginning
Mechanics	1.27	Beginning
Grand Mean	1.25	Beginning

The Grade 11 learners' first written composition reveals that their overall English writing proficiency is at the "Beginning" level across all key constructs: content, structure, lexico-grammatical, and mechanics. Specifically, in the content construct, they are still developing their ability to express ideas effectively. Their writing likely lacks depth and clarity, with limited organization and development of thoughts. Regarding structure, the learners struggle with organizing their writing logically. They likely face struggles to create coherent sentences and paragraphs, resulting in weak transitions between ideas and poor overall flow in their compositions. This underscores the need for more focused instruction on structuring written work logically and cohesively.

The lexico-grammatical construct suggests that the students have a limited grasp of vocabulary and grammar. Their writing is likely characterized by frequent errors in sentence construction, word choice, and grammatical usage, indicating a need for increased practice and instruction in these areas. Similarly, the mechanics constructs suggest that the learners struggle with basic writing conventions such as punctuation, capitalization, and spelling, which can significantly affect the clarity and readability of their compositions.

The grand mean of 1.25 confirms that the learners are at the "Beginning" level of English writing proficiency, meaning they have not yet mastered the essential skills for effective written communication. These results highlight a strong need for targeted interventions to improve their abilities in content development, organization, grammar, vocabulary, and writing mechanics. Instructional strategies that provide structured writing practice, along with constructive feedback, will be crucial for helping these students progress to higher levels of writing proficiency.

Part II. The Level of English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Learners During the Last Written Composition Per Construct

Table 3

The Level of English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Learners During the Last Written Composition Per Construct

Constructs	W1	W2	W3	W4	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content	2.27	2.88	3.04	3.31	2.88	Approaching Proficiency
Structure	1.92	2.88	2.92	2.85	2.64	Approaching Proficiency
Lexico-Grammatical	2.23	2.73	3.04	3.04	2.76	Approaching Proficiency
Mechanics	2.23	3.00	3.31	3.38	2.98	Approaching Proficiency
Grand Mean	2.16	2.87	3.08	3.15	2.81	Approaching Proficiency

The Grade 11 learners' final written compositions reveal significant progress in their English writing proficiency across the four key constructs: content, structure, lexico-grammatical, and mechanics. In terms of content, they have improved in organizing and expressing their ideas more clearly and effectively, demonstrating better development of thoughts compared to their initial efforts. Their writing now exhibits a more coherent presentation of ideas, though there remains room for further refinement to achieve full proficiency.

For structure, indicates that they have made progress in organizing sentences and paragraphs more logically, though challenges with coherence and transitions between ideas persist. The learners are still working on improving the overall flow of their writing but have advanced beyond the initial stages.

In the lexico-grammatical aspect, the learners use of vocabulary and grammar has improved, with fewer grammatical errors and more appropriate word choices, but there is still a need for further development to reach full proficiency.

In terms of mechanics, the learners reflect significant improvement in their ability to use punctuation, capitalization, and spelling correctly. Their written work is now clearer and more polished, with fewer mechanical errors, indicating that they are close to mastering these essential writing conventions.

Overall, the grand mean of 2.59 places the learners at the "Developing" level of writing proficiency. This demonstrates considerable strides since their initial compositions, moving beyond the beginning level. While they still need to refine certain areas, particularly in structure and grammar, the learners are on the right path to becoming proficient writers. Further practice and targeted instruction will help them continue to build on these gains and achieve full proficiency.

Part III. Significant Difference in the Level of English Writing Proficiency in First and Last Written Composition of the Respondents using the Theme Writing.

Table 4

Test of Significant Difference in the Level of English Writing Proficiency in First and Last Written Composition of the Respondents using the Theme Writing

Constructs	First		Last		Mean diff	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	mean	sd	mean	sd					
Content	1.31	0.47	2.85	0.925	-1.54	-	25	0.001	Significant
		1				10.3			
Structure	1.23	0.43	2.27	0.874	-1.04	-	25	0.001	Significant
		0				6.43			
Lexico-Grammatical	1.19	0.40	2.46	1.174	-1.27	-	25	0.001	Significant
		2				5.17			
Mechanics	1.27	0.45	2.27	0.710	-1.50	-	25	0.001	Significant
		2				10.0			
Total	5.00	1.75	9.85	3.683	-5.35	-	25	0.001	Significant
		5				31.9			

The test for significant differences in the level of English writing proficiency among Grade 11 learners between their first and last written compositions reveals statistically significant improvements across all constructs: content, structure, lexico-grammatical, and mechanics. The table shows that the learners' mean scores increased considerably from the first to the last composition, with p-values for each construct being 0.001, indicating that the changes are statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

For content, the mean increased from 1.31 in the first composition to 2.85 in the last, with a mean difference of -1.54 and a t-value of -10.3. This indicates a substantial improvement in the learners' ability to organize and present their ideas, with the significant difference suggesting that focused instruction and practice have had a meaningful impact.

Similarly, for structure, the mean increased from 1.23 to 2.27, with a mean difference of -1.04 and a t-value of -6.43. This improvement reflects the learners' enhanced ability to organize their compositions more logically and coherently. While progress was made, further refinement in structuring ideas is still necessary for full proficiency.

In the lexico-grammatical construct, the mean increased from 1.19 to 2.46, with a mean difference of -1.27 and a t-value of -5.17. This shows that the learners made significant progress in their use of vocabulary and grammar, though challenges in sentence construction and word choice still exist. Continued instruction in this area will be beneficial for achieving higher proficiency.

The mechanics construct also saw a significant improvement, with the mean increasing from 1.27 to 2.77, a mean difference of -1.50, and a t-value of -10.0. This suggests that the learners became more proficient in applying writing conventions, such as punctuation and spelling, with fewer errors in their final compositions.

Overall, the total mean score increased from 5.00 in the first composition to 9.85 in the last, with a mean difference of -5.35 and a t-value of -31.9, indicating a significant improvement in the learners' overall writing proficiency. The statistically significant differences across all constructs confirm that the learners made meaningful progress in their writing abilities, likely due to targeted instruction and practice throughout the course. These improvements highlight the effectiveness of the Theme Writing approach and suggest that the learners are on their way to developing stronger writing skills.

Part IV: Proposed Program for the Revival of Theme Writing

Based on the result of the study which revealed the effectiveness of Theme Writing in the level of English writing proficiency among Grade 11 learners at Bantad National High School, the proposed program for the revival of Theme Writing and the curriculum content in English for Academics and Professional Purposes are highly recommended.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results, the findings are summarized as follows:

1. The first written composition revealed the level of English writing proficiency of the respondents across all constructs.
 - 1.1 In terms of content, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Beginning"* with a mean score of 1.31;
 - 1.2 In terms of structure, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Beginning"* with a mean score of 1.23;
 - 1.3 In terms of lexico-grammatical, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Beginning"* with a mean score of 1.19; and
 - 1.4 In terms of mechanics, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Beginning"* with a mean score of 1.27.
2. The last written composition of the respondents showed significant improvement in their writing proficiency level per construct.
 - 2.1. In terms of content, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Approaching Proficiency"* with a mean score of 2.85;
 - 2.2 In terms of structure, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Developing"* with a mean score of 2.27;
 - 2.3 In terms of lexico-grammatical, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Developing"* with a mean score of 2.46; and
 - 2.4 In terms of mechanics, the level of English writing proficiency was *"Approaching Proficiency"* with a mean score of 2.77.

3. The comparison between the first and last written compositions revealed significant improvements in all constructs, with p-values of 0.001, indicating that the differences were statistically significant. The mean scores in areas such as content, structure, lexico-grammatical, and mechanics improved considerably, confirming that the learners made meaningful progress in their writing skills over time. Theme Writing and focused instruction likely contributed to these significant gains in proficiency. The proposed program for the revival of Theme Writing and revised curriculum content in English for Academics and Professional Purposes were proposed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the English writing proficiency level of the learners before the implementation of Theme Writing was at the "Beginning" level. However, by the end of the Theme Writing activities, their proficiency increased to the "Developing" and "Approaching Proficiency" levels. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, as there was a significant difference between the first and last written compositions using Theme Writing. Therefore, the effectiveness of Theme Writing in improving the English writing proficiency of Grade 11 learners at Bantad National High School is confirmed.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are made:

1. For the Department of Education Officials

The study's findings confirm the effectiveness of theme writing in enhancing the English writing proficiency of Grade 11 students. It highly recommends to revive the use of Theme writing as part of learning assessment and the revise of curriculum guide for the inclusion of Theme Writing in the EAPP curriculum. This will guide teachers in allocating specific time for developing students' writing skills before engaging in other academic writing activities. Also, it will help the students to develop their mechanics in writing over time.

2. For School Heads

The findings of the study highly recommend the use of Theme Writing as part of the school program to sustain the quality education in addressing the learning gap among SHS students.

3. For Teachers

This study strongly recommends the implementation of theme writing to assist Grade 11 students in practicing essential writing skills and addressing various writing difficulties highlighted in this research. Encouraging students to revise their original

outputs can raise awareness of their mistakes and help improve their overall proficiency level.

4. For Learners

Given the challenges learners faced in writing, theme writing may alleviate some of their struggles by gradually increasing their awareness of writing mistakes. Following the guidelines in theme writing and using the codes for editing their original work can help them acquire and apply the necessary skills to produce well-structured written texts.

5. For Future Researchers

This study can serve as a foundation for future research on theme writing, as there are limited related studies due to its recent introduction. Future researchers may also explore a comparative analysis of English writing proficiency between students in the Academic and TVL tracks. Additionally, further studies could be conducted on strategies for improving students' writing skills, areas that go beyond the scope and delimitations of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. No conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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